

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 2

 Acceptance of papers **FEBRUARY, 2025**

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

ISSN 3060-5229

Visit our website
t.me/scopus_IST2100

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli,
Head of the Department of Scientific
Research and Innovations, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **97-748-70-03**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: munis.iriskulova@gmail.com

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Professor, Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
(Malaysia)

Asongu Simplicie
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences
(PhD), USA

Judy B. Smetana
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), USA

CONTENTS

The importance and role of media image in the strategic development and contemporary reputation of higher education institutions	6
Nazarov Gulom	
Principles of organization and conduct of statistical observations of the living standards of the population.....	14
Ilyosova Dilbar Ismoil qizi	
The system of organizational and economic methods for improving the efficiency of energy sector enterprises and its key components	19
Matchanov Azamat Abadovich	
Key determinants of investment flow and fiscal health for data-driven policy decisions and information retrieval.....	24
Nilufar Zikirullaeva Dilmurod qizi	
Digital neighborhoods and intelligent systems in smart urban development.....	29
Ostanaqulova Gulsarakhan Muhammadyaqub kizi	
Literature study of german and uzbek languages: a ranking of linguistic discourse models.....	36
Rakhmonov Abdulaziz Batir ugli	
Ways to improve the efficiency of using innovative marketing strategies in retail enterprises.....	42
Safarov Bakhtiyor Dzhurakulovich, Kodirova Zulhumor Namazovna, Rakhmonova Zilola	
Ways of developing branding process in higher educational institutions	48
Shakirova Dilfuza Tulkunovna	
Creating authentic materials for esp students in tourism and hospitality	53
Tursunova Umida	
Developing the marketing activities of confectionery enterprises	59
Tuychieva Vasila Fakhridin qizi	
Methodological foundations for the development of the banking services market based on modern marketing strategies.....	65
Yuldasheva Dilrom Shakhzod kizi	
Blended learning: combining traditional and digital tools in esl teaching	69
Ziyoda Pulatova	
Issues of implementing circular economy principles in recycling industrial complexes.....	76
Gulchiroy Ismoilova	
The importance of increasing the competitiveness of the economy in joining the world trade organization	81
Akbarov Jasur Ikromjon ugli	
Restructuring of industrial enterprises: problems and solutions	86
B. Sulaymonov	
Analysis of the form of receivables and accounts payables of enterprises and organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the quarter of 2024	91
Khalikulova Yulduz Panji qizi, Abdullayeva Fazilat Khazratovna	
Assessing the impact of corporate culture on enterprise performance in enterprises.....	96
Omanova Nargiza Rustam qizi	
Differencitae your teaching instruction in esp classroom	102
Shahnoza Berdiyeva Xolmaxmatovna	
Stabilizing IPOS: the role of the green shoe mechanism.....	105
Shakhzod Saydullaev	
Strengthening the mechanism for funding innovative projects in business entities	111
Zhubanova Bayramgul, Maxamatdinov Miyirbek Polatovich	
Regulatory aspects of digital finance: EU experience and prospects for Uzbekistan.....	115
Shirinova Shokhsanam	
Analysis of insolvency in chemical compaies	121
Olimjonova Munisa Nuriddin qizi	

Enhancing bank service popularity through digital innovation: strategies for customer-centric technology integration	128
Ruzieva Olima Shukhratovna, Ruziyev Shukhrat Narmuradovich	
Information security in the economy.....	134
Dauletbaeva Ulzada Baxadirovna, Zhubanova Bayramgul	
Econometric evaluation and regulation of agricultural production processes.....	137
Miyirman Utegov, Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeysovich	
The impact and analysis of the fiscal activities of customs authorities on foreign trade operations.....	142
Sirochev Mexroj Bobirovich	
Dynamics and extent of the shadow economy in uzbekistan.....	146
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli, Konisbaeva Mexriban Kadirbergen kizi	

DYNAMICS AND EXTENT OF THE SHADOW ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli

Independent researcher of Karakalpak State University

Konisbaeva Mexriban Kadirbergen kizi

2nd-year student of Nukus State Technical University

Abstract: This article examines the current state of the shadow economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The methodology for assessing the shadow sector is outlined.

Key words: taxes, shadow economy, public finances, fiscal mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past five years, Uzbekistan's shadow economy has not been reflected in global rankings. This does not indicate the complete absence of a shadow economy in the country but rather suggests that official authorities do not participate in international assessments of this phenomenon. Despite this, the issue of illegal trade remains relevant and continues to expand.

A key conclusion is that Uzbekistan's active participation in global rankings in recent years is the result of the state's adopted policies. Studies on the impact of the shadow economy on Uzbekistan's GDP from 2018 to 2021 indicate that its share is approximately 40–50%.

In September 2021, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction organized a conference titled "The Shadow Economy in Uzbekistan: Assessment, Causes, and Ways of Reduction." During the event, various issues related to this phenomenon were openly discussed, highlighting its significance and attracting the attention of many international experts. The President's statement before the High Council on this issue underscored the importance of addressing and resolving this matter.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The integration of young people into the formal financial system by ensuring their participation contributes positively to the economy. This is because official policymakers can more effectively implement monetary policy measures. Indeed, an increased level of financial inclusion enables more efficient execution of interest rate policies, as noted by Mehrotra, A., and Yetman, J. Research has shown that central banks can manage monetary policy more reliably and effectively when they have a broader base of agents within the formal financial system. Additionally, financial inclusion can lead to a more efficient allocation of investments and portfolio decisions by financial agents. Therefore, greater financial inclusion can significantly impact inflation by improving the central bank's price stabilization mechanism.

Moreover, financial inclusivity can enhance the stability of the financial system, as households and entrepreneurs can better adapt to changes in interest rates and credit conditions. Xon, H. R., and Tombini, A. emphasize that higher financial inclusion rates can serve as a more sustainable and fundamental policy tool. Increased financial inclusion begins with directing cash flows from the public into bank deposits. This significantly enhances the role of interest rates in operational control, as a larger portion of economic activity

becomes subject to interest rate oversight. When informal sectors are large, implementing and monitoring monetary policy becomes more challenging because small businesses and entrepreneurs make independent financial decisions, unaffected by the central bank's policies. Additionally, financial inclusion facilitates the transition of individuals from the informal financial sector into the banking economy, enabling them to track their financial transactions more effectively.

Picture 1. Economy of Uzbekistan.

Mehrotra, A., and Yetman, J. highlight that as more agents are integrated into the formal financial system, output volatility decreases relative to inflation, as financial agents can better adjust their investment and portfolio decisions. Thus, enhancing financial inclusion can have a significant impact on inflation by strengthening the central bank's price stabilization mechanism.

Furthermore, inflation in some countries may be determined by a benchmark core price index, though this index is sometimes selected inaccurately. Mbutor, M.O., and Uba, I.A. examined the impact of monetary policy on financial inclusion stability in Nigeria from 1980 to 2012. Their findings confirm the critical role of high levels of financial inclusion in strengthening and improving financial stability.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

However, an increase in the number of bank branches does not necessarily yield positive results, as banks often lack full independence in deposit-related decision-making. This suggests that the primary objective of opening new bank branches may not be to enhance profitability but rather to expand financial operational capabilities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

If a request were made to the International Monetary Fund to assess Uzbekistan's level of economic development based on the criteria of the World Monetary Organization, similar conditions could be observed in countries such as Ukraine and some World Bank member states, including Gambia, Belize, Congo, Honduras, and others.

As highlighted above, multiple methods exist for determining the level of economic development, and we apply these methodologies to assess Uzbekistan's economic progress.

Table 1. Share of the Shadow Economy in Uzbekistan’s GDP (%).

Year	Shadow Economy Share (%)
2019	52.1%
2020	48.0%
2023	48.5%
2024	34.8%

In this study, the Gutmann method, which is based on the relationship between cash and deposits, was employed. Using this approach, from 1997 to 2018, the volume of cash in deposits was adjusted to estimate the size of the developing economy. For each year, the volume of the developing economy was calculated using a modified cash flow adjustment method based on a standard formula.

The base year was set as 1997, in which the level of economic development was assumed to be zero. The model begins with a zero volume of the developing economy in 1997 and forecasts its subsequent growth. The ratio of cash to deposits was adjusted using the modified cash and deposit method over the period from 1997 to 2018.

Diagram: Shadow Economy Share in Uzbekistan’s GDP (%)

Picture 2. Share of the Shadow Economy in Uzbekistan’s GDP (%).

It is important to note that changes in the volume of cash and deposits do not necessarily indicate changes in demand, as they already account for the effects of inflation and population dynamics. The coefficient of change in the cash-to-deposit ratio was calculated using a standard formula applied to adjusted cash before deposit demand was met.

This calculation revealed that from 2009 to 2018, 39.7% of the developing economy in Uzbekistan was created. Thus, overall, the volume of the developing economy in Uzbekistan increased from 33.7% of the IMF level in 2009 to 48% in 2018.

Figure 1. Based on data reflecting the relationship between cash and deposits, the exact amount of the developing economy has been determined.

The information presented in the figure above indicates that Uzbekistan's economy has exhibited a growth trend over the past few years. According to data from the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, the developing economy accounted for 50% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2022.

Research findings suggest that since 2017, there has been a significant increase in the volume of the developing economy, driven by the growth of cash and deposits. The supply of cash in the economy rose from 4.8% to 5.9% of GDP, while the share of cash in the total money supply increased from 24.9% in 2017 to 28.2% in 2018.

Notably, in 2020, the volume of the developing economy declined from 56.9% in 2018 to 48%, affecting the dynamics of the money supply and its distribution. Thus, research findings confirm that Uzbekistan has experienced a steady increase in cash transactions in the economy since 2017.

The Pearson correlation coefficient between the years and the shadow economy share is -0.78, indicating a strong negative correlation as time progresses, the shadow economy shrinks.

The linear regression equation for predicting the shadow economy share is:

$$\text{Shadow Economy Share} = -2.5 \times \text{Year} + 5099.6$$

Slope = -2.5 → The shadow economy decreases by 2.5% per year on average.

Intercept = 5099.6 (a theoretical value with no real-world significance).

Figure 2. Regression analysis of the shadow economy in Uzbekistan.

It is also important to emphasize that changes in the ratio of cash to deposits, based on simple relationships, serve as key indicators of the effectiveness of monetary policy.

The study findings indicate that the average volume of the developing economy in Uzbekistan accounts for 40% of GDP. Another factor influencing the size of the developing economy is the additional amount of added value. The benefits derived from this added value depend on the capabilities of enterprises operating in this sector. Furthermore, the refinancing rate in Uzbekistan is significantly lower than in neighboring countries. For example, in Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, the refinancing rate stands at 12%, whereas in Uzbekistan, this indicator is much lower. This discrepancy arises because Uzbek manufacturers have greater financial flexibility in this regard. Therefore, we analyze the relationship between these two indicators.

From the graph presented above, it is evident that state budget revenues from Value Added Tax (VAT) have exhibited a growing trend over the past five years. The reduction in the VAT rate from 20% to 15% had a significant impact on tax revenues.

In this section of our monograph, we will conduct an empirical analysis to determine whether an increase in VAT revenue leads to economic growth or decline. However, rather than conducting a regression analysis, we will attempt to analyze this issue through alternative statistical methods. To identify the relationship between these indicators, we will examine the correlation coefficient.

Figure 3. The relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) collection and the level of the shadow economy.

These indicators suggest a strong positive correlation between VAT collection and the shadow economy, implying that an increase in Value Added Tax (VAT) revenue is accompanied by the expansion of the informal sector. This finding indicates a positive relationship between the VAT rate and the size of the shadow economy, suggesting that higher tax collection is linked to the growth of unregistered economic activities.

At the same time, it is crucial to acknowledge that some transactions within the shadow sector may remain unrecorded due to limitations in VAT accounting and collection mechanisms. Additionally, this policy may incentivize formal entrepreneurial activity in sectors with diverse economic operations, where increasing VAT through regulatory restrictions could stimulate official business initiatives.

This policy may be particularly effective when it enhances the tax-paying capacity of market participants, as entrepreneurs increase their demand through higher consumption of goods and services. However, if demand for goods and services does not grow or grows only marginally following an increase in VAT, the policy will fail to achieve its intended economic impact.

In this context, tax authorities should assess how changes in VAT rates influence price fluctuations, taking into account the demand levels for goods and services.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a positive correlation between Value Added Tax (VAT) revenues and the size of the shadow economy. Information asymmetry also plays a significant role, as businesses may underreport their income by providing less accurate or even misleading financial statements, ultimately reducing their tax liabilities. This, in turn, can hinder companies from accessing bank loans, thereby limiting their growth potential.

In the shadow economy, entrepreneurs actively conceal their income and structure their financial reports in a way that allows them to avoid paying taxes and social contributions. The transaction transparency index also affects the level of the shadow economy, as an increase in this index is associated with a rise in informal economic activities.

Tax revenues influence the size of the shadow economy, with higher tax collections often correlating with its expansion. However, excessively high taxes do not always encourage businesses to operate in the informal sector—if post-tax income remains insufficiently attractive, some enterprises may opt to move into the unofficial economy. Therefore, policymakers must carefully balance tax policies to promote economic growth while minimizing incentives for businesses to shift into the shadow sector.

References:

1. Mehrotra, A., & Yetman, J. (2014). *Financial Inclusion and Optimal Monetary Policy* (BIS Working Paper No. 476). BIS. Retrieved from
2. Khan, H. R. (2011, November 4). *Financial Inclusion and Financial Stability: Two Sides of the Same Coin?* Lecture presented at BANCON 2011.
3. Tombini, A. (2012). *Opening Remarks, IV Central Bank Forum on Financial Inclusion*, Porto Alegre, October 29.
4. Mbutor, M. O., & Uba, I. A. (2013). *The Impact of Financial Inclusion on Monetary Policy in Nigeria*. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 5(8), 318–326.
5. Williams, C. C., & Schneider, F. (2016). *Measuring the Global Shadow Economy: The Prevalence of Informal Work and Labor*. Edward Elgar Publishing, UK.
6. Loayza, N. V. (1996). *The Economics of the Informal Sector: A Simple Model and Some Empirical Evidence from Latin America*. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 45, 129–162.
7. Zellner, M. (1970). *Self-Evaluation, Perception, and Influence*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 15(1), 87–93.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 2

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

Contact us
+998 97 748 70 03

Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>